

A Case–Control Study of Intrapartum Amnioinfusion in Meconium-Stained Liquor

Monalisa¹, Pallavi Singh²¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar²Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar

Received: 10-01-2024 / Revised: 13-02-2024 / Accepted: 10-03-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Monalisa

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Intrapartum amnioinfusion in meconium stained amniotic fluid has been known to dilute the meconium and prevent meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS). However, the literature available on intrapartum amnioinfusion is varying. The aim of this study was to investigate perinatal outcome and the rate of cesarean section (CS) following intrapartum amnioinfusion in women with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF).**Method:** A total of 100 women at term in labor with meconium were randomized to infuse transcervical intrapartum amnioinfusion with saline (50) and routine obstetrical care (50). Perinatal outcome and obstetric outcome were recorded and analyzed in both groups by means of Chi-square test.**Result:** The CS rate due to fetal distress was 40.0% in the control group and 20.0% in the study group. The difference was statistically significant (P 0.01). Respiratory distress of the neonate was significantly less common in the study group than in the control group (4.0% vs. 12%; P= 0.0349).**Conclusion:** Amnioinfusion in cases of meconium-stained liquor significantly improved neonatal outcome and CS rate without increasing any maternal and fetal complications.**Keywords:** Amnioinfusion, Amniotic fluid, Meconium.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) is a primary cause of respiratory morbidity in term and near-term neonates. [1] It has been reported that 5-12% of infants born with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF) develop MAS. [2] MSAF has been reported to increase the rate of operative interference in the form of cesarean section or instrumental delivery and increased need for resuscitation and MAS. [3] The risk of MAS has not been shown to reduce with prophylactic intrapartum oropharyngeal and nasopharyngeal suctioning; hence, intrapartum amnioinfusion was considered. [4,2]

Some studies have proposed transcervical amnioinfusion as a means for reducing the complications. [5] Amnioinfusion is a process in which normal saline is infused into the uterine cavity to replace the amniotic fluid and is used to treat decreased inter-amniotic volume, oligohydramnios, and fetal distress. Intracervical instillation of normal saline into the uterus during labor decreases the concentration of meconium in the amniotic fluid, thereby reducing the occurrence of MAS. It is also used to treat reduced intra-

amniotic volume including prophylactic treatment of oligohydramnios and fetal distress during labor. [6] A lower incidence of MAS, cesarean deliveries, and perinatal mortality after amnioinfusion were reported in a systemic review of randomized trials; however, these trials had small sample size and had no clearly defined outcomes. [7] Moreover, some authors did not validate these advantages in their studies. [8,9] Available literature concerning the advantages of amnioinfusion in MSAF are variable. Hence, a case-control study was conducted to assess the neonatal outcomes following intrapartum transcervical amnioinfusion in full-term pregnant women.

Aims and Objectives

The present study was conducted in Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar with the following objectives:

1. To study perinatal outcome following IAI in patients with meconium-stained liquor.
2. To assess the rate of cesarean deliveries following intrapartum transcervical amnioinfusion.

sion in women with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSAF).

3. The two groups were matched for gravidity and parity.

Material and Method

The current study was conducted Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar from January 2021 to December 2021.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were as follows:

Inclusion Criteria

Women in labor with thick meconium staining of the amniotic fluid; a single fetus in the cephalic presentation with a gestational age of 37 weeks or more; ruptured membranes; cervical dilatation between 3 and 8 cm; and no indication for urgent delivery (e.g., loss of FHR variability and late decelerations) were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Women were excluded if there was a major fetal anomaly, chorioamnionitis, antepartum hemorrhage, hepatitis B or C, active genital herpes, polyhydramnios, indication for urgent delivery (cord prolapse, and severe fetal bradycardia), or an inability to comprehend the consent form.

A total of 100 women were randomly assigned at a ratio of 1:1 to either amnioinfusion or standard care (fetal heart was monitored by Doppler and Cardiotocography). A sterile catheter was introduced transcervically to a depth of 30 cm, and a bolus of 600 ml of sterile saline at room temperature was infused under the force of gravity at a rate of 20 ml/min over a period of 30 min. More fluid was infused at the same rate till the returning fluid is clear or up to a maximum of 1,000 ml. The control group was not given any IAI. Women were assessed by uterine palpation at 15-min intervals for uterine hypertonic contractions. In such cases, amnioinfusion was discontinued. Continuous electronic FHR monitoring was performed in both groups. Augmentation for inadequate uterine contraction was done with use of Oxytocin if there was a delay in the progress of labor and no fetal Bradycardia recorded. Emergency CS was done when fetal Bradycardia was recorded or in case of non-progress of labor. Careful suctioning of the oro-pharynx and nasopharynx was performed before presentation of the shoulders and again immediately after delivery. Laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation and suctioning were reserved for infants with respiratory depression requiring positive-pressure ventilation. The composite primary outcome measure was the occurrence of perinatal death, moderate or severe meconium aspiration syndrome, or both. In accordance with clinical criteria, the meconium aspiration syndrome

was defined as respiratory distress in the first 4 h after birth and categorized as severe (requiring assisted mechanical ventilation) or moderate (requiring oxygen for at least 48 h at a concentration of 40 % or greater but without mechanical ventilation). Secondary outcomes included perinatal death or maternal death or serious morbidity or both. Serious perinatal morbidity included moderate or severe meconium aspiration syndrome; hypotonia; assisted ventilation or intubation of more than 5 min duration; a 5-min Apgar score below 7; an umbilical-artery blood pH value below 7.05; abnormal consciousness; the need for tube feeding; convulsions; and a blood or lumbar culture positive for bacteria. Serious maternal morbidity included the presence of any of the following: uterine rupture, amniotic-fluid embolism, antepartum hemorrhage requiring urgent delivery, postpartum hemorrhage. Requiring transfusion, hysterectomy, admission to the intensive care unit, or disseminated intravascular coagulation.

The FHR tracings were categorized as normal, as having abnormalities of insufficient severity to justify clinical intervention, or as having abnormalities requiring clinical intervention. The presence of decreased heart rate variability with late or prolonged decelerations was considered reason for intervention.

All women were analyzed according to the group to which they had been randomly assigned. We used Student's t test to compare continuous variables and the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. The effects of the intervention were expressed as relative risks with their 95% confidence intervals. We used the SAS statistical software package (version 8.0).

Results

A total of 100 women were studied, 50 in each group. The two groups were comparable with respect to age, duration of pregnancy, pregnancy complications, and labor characteristics as seen in Table 1.

Table 2 shows the outcome of the study along with statistical analysis of the results. The CS rate due to fetal distress was 40.0 % in the control group and 20.0 % in the study group. The difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). Apgar score ≤ 5 at 1 min was 12.0 % in the control group compared to 4.0 % in the study group ($P = 0.06$). The 5-min Apgar score was also better ($P = 0.29$) in the study group. The rate of meconium aspiration syndrome was 5.0 % in the control group and 2.5 % in the amnioinfusion group.

Respiratory distress of the neonate was significantly less common in the study group than in the control group (4.0 % vs. 12 %; $P = 0.0349$).

Laryngoscopic finding of meconium below the vocal cords in neonates was 36 % in the control group compared to only 6.0 % in the study group.

The difference was statistically significant ($P \leq 0.001$) indicating thereby that meconium aspiration would have been much higher if IAI was not given.

Also respiratory distress and MAS were higher in the control group. There were no perinatal deaths in the study group as well as the control group. Postpartum fever was more or less at equal rate in both groups. There was no increase in neonatal infection rate. There was no case of hypertonic uterine contractions.

Table 1: Baseline Data

Characteristics	Study group (n=50)	Control group (n=50)
Average age (years)	24.3 (range 18–32.3)	23.0 (range 17.1–35.0)
Average gestational age (weeks)	38.7 (range 36.4–40.0)	37.9 (range 36.0–40.3)
Average birth weight (kg)	2.5 (range 2.0–2.80)	2.6 (range 2.2–2.9)
Pregnancy complications		
• Post term	4	5
• IUGR	3	0
• PIH	5	4
Average cervical dilatation (cm) at the time of amnioinfusion	4.9 (range 4.2–6.1)	5.1 (range 4.0–6.9)
Average time interval between amnioinfusion and delivery (h)	2.6 (range 2.3–3.6)	2.9 (range 2.3–3.6)

Table 2: Comparison of outcomes in study and control group

Outcome	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		V ²	p-value
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage		
Cesarean section for fetal distress	10	20	20	40	10.47	0.0012
Instrumental delivery	4	8	10	20	0.05	NS
Apgar score						
• 1 min	2	4	6	12	3.39	0.0656
• 5 min	2	4	2	4	1.10	0.2943
Respiratory distress	2	4	6	12	4.45	0.0349
Meconium below the vocal cords	6	12	18	39	24.15	1
Meconium aspiration syndrome	3	6	5	10	2.25	0.0001
Perinatal death	0	0	0	8	0	0
Maternal pyrexia	4	8	5	10	0.23	0.6315

Discussion

The two groups matched in all respects including the prevalence of IUGR and post-dated pregnancy which are considered as confounding variables for both passage of meconium and MAS. In our study, in the amnioinfusion group, rate of CS was significantly less ($P \leq 0.01$) as has also been reported by Das et al. [10] and Sahu. [11] Similarly, in a study by Rathorea et al. [12], the CS rate in amnioinfusion group was significantly lower (21 %) compared with the control group (36 %) with relative risk (RR) of 0.47. In our study, respiratory distress was significantly lower in the study group ($P = 0.03$). The incidence of MAS was 2.1 % in the study group and 9.47 % in the control group ($P = 0.06$), which are also comparable to those reported by Rathorea et al. Meconium below the vocal cords was significantly higher ($P \leq 0.001$) in the control group similar to the findings of Das et al. and Rathorea et al. [10] Rathorea found that amnioinfusion was associated with a significant decrease in the incidence of meconium at the vocal cords ($P = 0.001$): improvement in 1-min apgar

scores ($P \leq 0.05$), respiratory distress ($P = 0.002$), and fewer admissions to nursery as compared with the controls. On the contrary, Fraser et al. in his study found that amnioinfusion did not reduce the risk of meconium aspiration syndrome or perinatal death. There were no perinatal deaths in the current study in both the groups, which was different from the findings of Rathorea et al. [12], who reported 2 % perinatal deaths in their study group and 5 % in the control group. In spite of intrauterine catheter introduction and saline infusion, the incidence of puerperal pyrexia was lower in the study group. The decrease is probably due to dilutional effect on bacteria that enter the uterus. Rathorea et al. and Hofmeyr [10,13] also found similar results.

A study by Fraser et al. [14] showed that the rates of perinatal death, moderate or severe meconium aspiration syndrome, or both did not differ according to whether amnioinfusion was or was not performed. However, as has already been discussed, many studies have proved the efficacy of amnioinfusion in preventing MAS and in decreasing the CS rate as seen in this study also.

Amnioinfusion is only one of a number of interventions aimed at reducing the risk of the meconium aspiration syndrome. Others include electronic fetal heart-rate monitoring, operative delivery in selected cases and airway support in the newborn period. The relative benefits of amnioinfusion could depend on the pattern of use of these co-interventions. Amnioinfusion reduces high vagal stimulation because of correction of oligohydramnios resulting from rupture of membranes.

Cord compression-induced vagal stimulation is also decreased. These probably decrease further meconium passage as well as remove a stimulus for deep fetal breathing and gasping. IAI also has a dilution effect on the meconium. Thus, it decreases meconium in the trachea and reduces the incidence of MAS and birth asphyxia.

Conclusion

We found that the CS rate in the amnioinfusion group was significantly less as compared to the control group. The rate of meconium aspiration syndrome and respiratory distress was also significantly less in the study group as compared to the control group. There was no increase in maternal and neonatal infection rates and other complications due to amnioinfusion in our study. Therefore, intra-partum intrauterine amnioinfusion is a beneficial procedure using simple equipment in the absence of modern electronic fetal-monitoring facilities especially in low-resource settings.

References

1. Dargaville PA, Copnell B, Australian and New Zealand Neonatal Network. The epidemiology of meconium aspiration syndrome: Incidence, risk factors, therapies, and outcome. *Pediatrics* 2006; 117:1712-21.
2. Wiswell TE, Gannon CM, Jacob J, Goldsmith L, Szlyd E, Weiss K, et al. Delivery room management of the apparently vigorous meconium-stained neonate: Results of the multicenter, international collaborative trial. *Pediatrics* 2000; 105:1-7.
3. Shaikh EM, Mehmood S, Shaikh MA. Neonatal outcome in meconium stained amniotic fluid-one year experience. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2010; 60:711-4.
4. Vain NE, Szlyd EG, Prudent LM, Wiswell TE, Aguilar AM, Vivas NI. Oropharyngeal and nasopharyngeal suctioning of meconium-stained neonates before delivery of their shoulders: multicentre randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 2004; 364:597-602.
5. Bhatia P, Reena K, Sangita N. Role of intrapartum transcervical amnioinfusion in patients with meconium-stained amniotic fluid. *J Obstet Gynaecol India*. 2013; 63:59-63.
6. Bansal N, Gupta V, Nanda A, Chaudhary P, Tandon A, Behl N. Intrapartum Amnioinfusion in Meconium-Stained Liquor: A Case²Control Study. *J Obstet Gynaecol India*. 2013; 63:164-7.
7. Hofmeyr GJ. Amnioinfusion for meconium-stained liquor in labor. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2002; (1):CD000014.
8. Xu H, Hofmeyr J, Roy C, Fraser WD. Intrapartum amnioinfusion for meconium-stained amniotic fluid: A systematic review of randomised controlled trials. *BJOG*. 2007; 114:383-90.
9. Pierce J, Gaudier FL, Sanchez-Ramos L. Intrapartum amnioinfusion for meconium-stained fluid: Meta-analysis of prospective clinical trials. *Obstet Gynecol* 2000; 95:1051-6.
10. Das V, Shrivastava S, Preetikumar, et al. Amnioinfusion during labor complicated by meconium. *J Obstet Gynecol India*. 2001;51:105-7.
11. Sahu IM. Intrapartum amnio-infusion for meconium stained amniotic fluid. *J Obstet Gynecol India*. 2003; 53:345-7.
12. Rathorea AM, Singh R, Ramji S, et al. Randomized trial of amnioinfusion during labor with meconium stained amniotic fluid. *BJOG*. 2002; 109:17-20.
13. Hofmeyr GJ. Amnioinfusion for meconium stained liquor in labor. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2000 ;(2):CD 000014.
14. Fraser WD, Hofmeyr J, Lede R, et al. Amnioinfusion for the prevention of the meconium aspiration syndrome. *NEJM*. 2005; 353: 909-17.